

CORONAVIRUS IN POULTRY AND HUMAN IN PARALLEL STANCE

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What is coronavirus? It is large family of single stranded viruses (there is lipid envelop around its genome, which make it vulnerable to be killed with common disinfectants). There are spike like protein projections on its surface which give them crown like appearance (corona word means crown). It is further divided into 4 genera. Human common cold, cats, dogs, swine and bats viruses belong to alpha strain. Severe acute respiratory syndrome 1 and 2 along with middle east respiratory syndrome, cattle, bat, horse and swine viruses belongs to beta strain. Baluga whale and poultry viruses belongs to gamma strain. Wild birds and swine viruses belong to delta strain. There is common bluster myth being seen in our society that it transfers from eating poultry meat, which is totally wrong as

hormone usage myth in poultry. Although it is pandemic which means it spread in multiple countries with large number of infected patients. Diseases which transfer from animals to humans are called zoonotic diseases. Poultry corona virus belongs to gamma strain whereas human corona virus belongs to beta strain. Zoonotic potential of corona depends on similarity of binding receptor. In human SARS-2 binds with ACE-2 receptor, which resembles 65% with chicken ACE-2 receptor. There are two main diseases of poultry which are caused by coronavirus named as Infectious bronchitis virus (IBV) and Turkey corona virus which is commonly known as blue comb. Both of these are not transfer from poultry to humans their causative agent gamma virus is host specific which is avian cell.

Infectious bronchitis virus disease of poultry is highly contagious, first time reported in 1930 in chickens but it is still endemic in United States poultry industry. It is acute respiratory disease, effects young birds, with low mortality round about <5% but morbidity rate is much higher. Its incubation period is 36 hours and persist for 2 to 3 weeks. It cannot be diagnosed or confirmed on clinical signs (weakness, depression, Sneezing and cough) only, further serological tests are compulsory to make a potent diagnosis. Its other strains also exist which affects kidney (nephrotropic), affects oviduct (reproductive) which leads to decrease eggs production with eggs shape abnormalities. Infected birds shed this virus in feaces along with nasal and oral secretions up to 20 weeks because it stays in ceca. It spreads through air respiratory droplets, contact with infected bird, equipment and drinking water. The IBV binds with sialic acid receptor in chickens, avian species sialic acid receptor site shape is cone like whereas in mammals (humans) its shape is umbrella like. This thing clearly shows that it cannot be transferred to humans due to difference of binding receptor site shape.

Trachea with excessive amount of mucus

Turkey corona virus also known as blue comb and transmissible enteritis. It was first discovered in 1951 but become major problem in 1970 and still present endemically in

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United States. It results in acute enteritis, mainly effects young age (less than 4 weeks) birds. Its morbidity is 100% but mortality varies depending in severity ranges between 5-50%. Its incubation period is 2-3 days can prolong to 5 days whereas clinical signs last after 2 weeks.

Infected birds shows huddling, cyanosis, watery droppings and depression. Birds shows stunted growth in young ones, adult birds are also affected but the severity is less acute. Egg's production suddenly drops and egg becomes choky. Virus shed from feces of birds up to 6 weeks. It can be transferred by vector like flies and beetles. This virus is not potentially antigenic like IBV.

Coronavirus disease treatments in poultry- there is no specific drug to treat these IBV and TCV but antibiotics are being used to protect from secondary bacterial infection. Vaccine (live and killed) against IBV is not effective because it changes itself genetically (80 strains detected in world). For Turkey corona virus there is no vaccine until now. Birds can be infected with virus without showing illness signs but animal shed virus in feces, because signs appear after incubation period. Mode of transmission is aerosol, ingestion, contact with mucus membrane, fomites and vectors (flies, rodents and beetles). Biosecurity is key factor to prevent coronavirus diseases in poultry.

Small intestine contents with watery and cecal contents frothy

Coronavirus in humans is not a new thing it spilled over earlier two times namely SARS-1 and MERS, both of these are acute respiratory diseases. The mortality rate was 10 and 35% in SARS1 and MERS. The SARS-1 was originated from China, an animal called civet and spreads in humans.

Corona Virus

The MERS was originated in middle east countries, originated from bats and transferred through camel (vector). Currently pandemic SARS-2 is spilled over from bats, pangolin, snakes but not cleared yet. Its incubation period is 5-7 days on average but average is up to 14 days. According to world health organization 136 situation report published on 4 June, 2020 total number of coronavirus cases were 6,416,828 along with 1,29,281 deaths worldwide. Its symptoms are fever, tiredness, cough, headache, loss of taste and

smell and diarrhea. The similarity between SARS-2 and IBV is 54%, whereas spike protein S1 similarity is 26%. Antibodies produced in recovered person persists for 2-3 years post infection. To stop SARS-2 it is mandatory that 70 to 80% population should be infected with it whereas according to recent WHO report 5-8% of total population is infected in most of countries.

There are two patterns in new virus evolution naming as antigenic shift and antigenic drift. Maximum rate of mutation is found in influenza virus which is round about 50 mutations per year. Infectious bronchitis virus of poultry shows 36 to 39 mutations per year, whereas SARS-2 shows 25 mutations per year according to updated data.

The important thing is that every mutation does not impact on transmission and virulence of virus.

How does respiratory viruses spread from one person to other? Aerosol (small liquid particles suspend in airs, stay more time in air) and droplet (large liquid droplet, it required direct contact and indirect route if someone touches its mouth or nose). It is generally considered that a person infected with virus produces 200,000,000 viral particles per droplet per sneeze. In case of SARA-2 it is estimated 1000 viral particles are required to make someone sick. A single cough in humans produces round about 3000 droplets (large particles falls earlier whereas small particles stay in air and spread in room) which can travel 50mph. A single sneeze can produce 30,000 droplets which can travels 200mph and stays more time in room air. Even breathing produce droplets round about 50 to 5000 depending upon intensity.

From above discussion on coronavirus disease in poultry and humans, their mode of transmission and receptor attachment, it can be concluded that coronavirus diseases of poultry like IBV and TCV are not zoonotic. You can eat chicken meat without any hesitation of being affected with COVID19.

Stop spreading such fake news without any scientific background. To fight with COVID19 strong immune system is required and poultry meat helps to boost up immunity at cheaper rate than any other protein source.

